

Research Article

A Decision-Making Tool for Supplier Selection Using Entropy-WASPAS Method

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Abstract: Choosing the right supplier is a complex decision-making process since it involves multiple conflicting criteria. The chosen supplier must be able to consistently provide quality products and services that meet the requirements of the business. The efficient supplier is able to help businesses maintain high performance, minimize risks, and build a competitive advantage in the market. Traditionally, decision-makers may base the selection process on their preference, past relationship with the supplier, the tender process, and the supplier's reputation. The multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) method, specifically the Entropy-Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment (Entropy-WASPAS) method, makes the decision-making process more organized and transparent. The hybridized method is proposed as a decision-making tool to enhance decision-making accuracy. The Entropy method is applied to obtain the weight of criteria, and the WASPAS method is used to rank and to select the most efficient supplier based on predetermined criteria. Businesses or any interested parties can receive consultation services that assist them in data collection and model implementation. Certification and training are also one way to commercialize this method as an efficient decision-making tool.

Keywords: Entropy; WASPAS; Decision-making.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A right supplier can guarantee the business long-term growth. They help by reducing the procurement costs if they deliver quality products and services. Poor-quality products from unreliable suppliers may lead to customer dissatisfaction, thus affecting the brand's reputation and its profitability. Choosing the right supplier is a complex decision-making process since it involves numerous contradictory criteria. The purchasing managers are responsible for choosing the reliable supplier. Traditionally, the decision is done through a tender process or influenced by the supplier's reputation, the decision-maker's preference, or their past relationship with the supplier. Traditional selection methods often rely heavily on human judgment, which can introduce subjectivity and inconsistency, especially when multiple criteria are involved. With the help of multi-criteria decision-

making (MCDM) methods, specifically the Entropy-Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment (Entropy-WASPAS) method, the decision-making process becomes more organized, accurate, and transparent.

The WASPAS method is introduced by (Zavadskas et al., 2012). It is a utility-based ranking approach that combines two MCDM methods, which are the Weighted Sum Method (WSM) and the Weighted Product Method (WPM). The authors stated that the joint methods are able to increase the ranking accuracy. The accuracy of the WASPAS method is estimated to increase up to 1.3 times when compared to the WPM method and up to 1.6 times when compared to the WSM method. On the other hand, Chakraborty and Zavadskas (2014) found that the WASPAS method gives rankings of options that are nearly as accurate as those from previous studies when used in eight real-world manufacturing problems. Its results closely matched or improved upon those from other MCDM methods like AHP, GTMA, VIKOR, PROMETHEE, and ELECTRE. The authors also analyzed the effect of parameter λ on the ranking performance, which revealed that better performance is obtained at higher λ values. When the value of λ is 0, the WASPAS method mimics the WPM method, and when λ is 1, it is transformed into the WSM method. The WASPAS method showed strong resistance to rank reversal of the considered alternatives. Researchers also find that this method uniquely handles both single- and multi-response optimization problems in various machining operations. The method is simple in computation (Menekşe & Akdağ, 2023), and its effectiveness provides researchers with the flexibility to apply or extend it (Zavadskas et al., 2025).

Despite its advantage, the WASPAS method lacks information on how to determine the weights of the criteria. The weights play an important role in determining the ranking of the alternatives. In this project, the Entropy method, which is an objective weighting method, is integrated with the WASPAS method. Shannon introduced the Entropy method in 1948 as a measure of uncertainty in the theory of information (Zhang et al., 2022). The Entropy method is applied due to its advantage of avoiding the interference of decision-makers, hence making it less biased (Goswami et al., 2022). This method is free from inconsistency and does not require consistency checking of the subjective opinion of the decision-makers (Goswami et al., 2022).

The combined method is proposed to advance the advantages of these two MCDM methods. Thus, the objectives of this project are (1) to implement the Entropy-WASPAS as a decision-making tool and (2) to enhance decision-making accuracy with the Entropy-WASPAS method.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This decision-making process involves three main phases. The first phase is data collection. Figure 1 shows the constructed decision matrix, which consists of the collected data. In this phase, data related to the predetermined criteria and the list of potential supplier options are gathered and entered into a prepared Microsoft Excel file. Microsoft Excel is suitable for users without coding experience, as it offers a user-friendly interface and requires no programming knowledge. The formulas can be adjusted easily to test various scenarios, and calculations can be performed using built-in Excel functions.

Objective <input type="text" value="Select the best supplier"/>					
	Criteria 1	Criteria 2	Criteria 3	Criteria 4	Criteria 5
	Benefit	Cost	Benefit	Benefit	Benefit
Alternative 1	5	3	5	3	5
Alternative 2	2	12	4	2	5
Alternative 3	2	5	4	5	3
Sum	9	20	13	10	13

Figure 1. Decision matrix.

The second phase involved the implementation of the Entropy method to obtain the weights of the criteria. The decision matrix is first normalized. Subsequently, the entropy values and the degree of divergence are calculated. Finally, the weights of the criteria are computed. The process involved is shown in Figure 2. Figure 2 shows the normalized decision matrix and the weights of the criteria. Once the weights are obtained, the values are used as the input in the framework of the WASPAS method.

Objective <input type="text" value="Select the best supplier"/>						
	Criteria 1	Criteria 2	Criteria 3	Criteria 4	Criteria 5	
	Benefit	Cost	Benefit	Benefit	Benefit	
Alternative 1	0.55556	0.15	0.38462	0.3	0.38462	
Alternative 2	0.22222	0.6	0.30769	0.2	0.38462	
Alternative 3	0.22222	0.25	0.30769	0.5	0.23077	
Sum	1	1	1	1	1	
Entropy	0.90571	0.85347	0.99474	0.93723	0.97705	
Degree of divergence	0.09429	0.14653	0.00526	0.06277	0.02295	0.3318
Criteria weight	0.28417	0.44161	0.01586	0.18918	0.06918	1
Ranking	2	1	5	3	4	

Figure 2. Normalized decision matrix and the weights of the criteria.

In the third phase, the Entropy-WASPAS method is implemented to rank and to select the supplier with respect to the multiple conflicting criteria. The decision matrix is once again normalized, and the values of the relative importance based on WSM and WPM methods are determined. Then, the values of the relative importance by using the WASPAS method are obtained. The supplier is then selected based on the values of the relative importance. Figure 3 shows the ranking of suppliers based on the WASPAS method and highlights the most efficient supplier.

Objective	Select the best supplier								
	Criteria weight	0.28417	0.44161	0.01586	0.18918	0.06918			
	Criteria 1	Criteria 2	Criteria 3	Criteria 4	Criteria 5				
	Benefit	Cost	Benefit	Benefit	Benefit	WSM	WPM	WASPAS	Ranking
Alternative 1	1	1	1	0.6	1	0.92433	0.90789	0.91611	1
Alternative 2	0.4	0.25	0.8	0.4	1	0.38161	0.35013	0.36587	3
Alternative 3	0.4	0.6	0.8	1	0.6	0.62201	0.59165	0.60683	2

Figure 3. Ranking of suppliers.

3. FINDINGS

This approach is considered a cost-effective solution for conducting MCDM analysis, such as the Entropy-WASPAS method. The most efficient supplier can be selected once the data is entered into the Microsoft Excel file. The process is straightforward and simple. The decision-makers or any interested parties can make informed, organized, and accurate decisions even though they have little or almost no knowledge about the MCDM methods.

4. DISCUSSION

The Entropy-WASPAS method is found to be a powerful decision-making tool. The findings also highlight the advantage of the WASPAS method in producing an accurate decision.

5. CONCLUSION

The Entropy-WASPAS method is an effective decision-making tool. It offers significant benefits to the users and the decision-makers due to its simple computation process and cost-effective approach. It allows for easy adaptation, even for those without programming experience, when implemented using familiar platforms like Microsoft Excel. This method can be extended to various selection problems.

To further enhance its impact, the Entropy-WASPAS method holds strong commercialization potential. Businesses or any interested parties can receive consultation services that assist them in data collection and model implementation. Another promising approach is to offer certification and training programs, targeting professionals, students, and organizations aiming to adopt data-driven decision-making practices. The development of a user-friendly software tool or Excel-based template can make the method widely accessible to non-technical users.

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